

Balaji Venkateswaran Venkatasubramanian, Christos Laoudias, Mathaios Panteli
KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

Vienna, Austria & Online | 3-8 May 2026

1. Motivation

- Extreme windstorms can cause severe damage to physical assets (e.g., overhead lines, trees) and trigger cascading failures across interconnected infrastructures.
- Interdependencies among power, telecommunication, and transportation systems amplify the disruption and societal impact.
- Traditional approaches rely on static, historical data, limiting preparedness; AI enables scalable analysis of complex cascading risks.

2. Objectives

- Develop an AI-powered Digital Twin (DT) framework for windstorm emergency management.
- Integrate physics-based windstorm simulation with cascading impact analysis in a unified digital environment.
- Use Generative AI (GenAI) as a post-simulation analytical layer for vulnerability and risk analysis.
- Support decision-making through stress-testing, risk identification, and response planning under future windstorm scenarios.

Key Advantage:

Preserves physical consistency of the Digital Twin (DT) while leveraging AI for efficiency, generalization, and rapid risk assessment.

3. AI-Powered Digital Twin Framework

4. Case Study Application on Cyprus Critical Infrastructure System

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program through the project Solid Preparedness And Resilience for Robust Operations during disaster Wilderness (SPARROW) (Grant agreement ID: 101168499).

5. Key Findings

- The hybrid physics-AI DT effectively captures complex, nonlinear relationships between wind events and cascading infrastructure failures.
- Enables rapid identification of vulnerable assets and risk hotspots across interconnected infrastructures.
- Supports stress-testing under a wide range of plausible future windstorm scenarios.
- Provides actionable insights for national-level emergency and crisis management.

6. Conclusion

- This work presents a hybrid physics-based and AI-enhanced Digital Twin framework for windstorm emergency management in interconnected critical infrastructures.
- The framework offers a flexible and extensible foundation to improve resilience to climate-driven hazards and support decision-making across all stages of emergency management.